

Gene Panel for Analysis

1. Negative Controls: Housekeeping Genes

Ribosomal Large Subunit

RPL3, RPL4, RPL5, RPL6, RPL7, RPL7A, RPL8, RPL9, RPL10, RPL10A, RPL11, RPL12, RPL13, RPL13A, RPL14, RPL15, RPL17, RPL18, RPL18A, RPL19, RPL21, RPL22, RPL23, RPL23A

Ribosomal Small Subunit

RPS2, RPS3, RPS3A, RPS4X, RPS4Y1, RPS5, RPS6, RPS7, RPS8, RPS9, RPS10, RPS11, RPS12, RPS13, RPS14, RPS15, RPS15A, RPS16, RPS17, RPS18, RPS19, RPS20, RPS21

Cytoskeletal Actin

ACTB, ACTG1, ACTA1, ACTA2, ACTC1, ACTN1, ACTN2, ACTN4, PFN1, PFN2

Cytoskeletal Tubulin

TUBA1A, TUBA1B, TUBA1C, TUBA3C, TUBA3D, TUBA4A, TUBA8, TUBB, TUBB1, TUBB2A, TUBB2B, TUBB3, TUBB4A, TUBB4B, TUBB6

Glycolysis

HK1, HK2, GPI, PFKM, PFKP, PFKL, ALDOA, ALDOB, ALDOC, TPI1, GAPDH, PGK1, PGK2, PGAM1, PGAM2, ENO1, ENO2, ENO3, PKM, PKLR, LDHA, LDHB, LDHC

TCA Cycle

CS, ACO1, ACO2, IDH1, IDH2, IDH3A, IDH3B, IDH3G, OGDH, SUCLA2, SUCLG1, SUCLG2, SDHA, SDHB, SDHC, SDHD, FH, MDH1, MDH2

Mitochondrial Complex I

NDUFA1, NDUFA2, NDUFA3, NDUFA4, NDUFA5, NDUFA6, NDUFA7, NDUFA8, NDUFA9, NDUFA10, NDUFA11, NDUFA12, NDUFA13, NDUFB1, NDUFB2, NDUFB3, NDUFB4, NDUFB5, NDUFB6

Mitochondrial Complex IV

COX4I1, COX4I2, COX5A, COX5B, COX6A1, COX6A2, COX6B1, COX6B2, COX6C, COX7A1, COX7A2, COX7A2L, COX7B, COX7C, COX8A, COX8C

ATP Synthase

ATP5F1A, ATP5F1B, ATP5F1C, ATP5F1D, ATP5F1E, ATP5MC1, ATP5MC2, ATP5MC3, ATP5MD, ATP5ME, ATP5MF, ATP5MG, ATP5PB, ATP5PD, ATP5PF, ATP5PO

Heat Shock Proteins

HSPA1A, HSPA1B, HSPA1L, HSPA2, HSPA4, HSPA4L, HSPA5, HSPA6, HSPA8, HSPA9, HSPA12A, HSPA12B, HSPA13, HSP90AA1, HSP90AB1, HSP90B1, HSPH1

2. Monoamine Systems

Dopamine Receptors

DRD1, DRD2, DRD3, DRD4, DRD5

Dopamine Synthesis & Metabolism

TH, DDC, COMT, MAOA, MAOB, DBH, GCH1, PTS, QDPR, SPR

Dopamine Transport & Signaling

SLC6A3, SLC18A1, SLC18A2, PPP1R1B, GNAL, ADCY5, PDE1B, PDE10A

Serotonin Receptors

HTR1A, HTR1B, HTR1D, HTR1E, HTR1F, HTR2A, HTR2B, HTR2C, HTR3A, HTR3B, HTR3C, HTR3D, HTR3E, HTR4, HTR5A, HTR5BP, HTR6, HTR7

Serotonin Synthesis & Metabolism

TPH1, TPH2, SLC6A4, AANAT, ASMT

Norepinephrine Receptors

ADRA1A, ADRA1B, ADRA1D, ADRA2A, ADRA2B, ADRA2C, ADRB1, ADRB2, ADRB3

Norepinephrine Synthesis & Transport

PNMT, SLC6A2

Histamine System

HRH1, HRH2, HRH3, HRH4, HDC, HNMT, SLC22A3

Trace Amine Receptors

TAAR1, TAAR2, TAAR5, TAAR6, TAAR8, TAAR9

Monoamine Signaling

GNB1, GNB2, GNB3, GNB4, GNB5, GNG2, GNG3, GNG4, GNG7, GNG11, GNG12, ADCY1, ADCY2, ADCY7, ADCY8, ADCY9, PDE4A, PDE4B, PDE4C, PDE4D

Vesicular Transport

SYT1, SYT2, SYT4, SYT7, SYT11, SNAP25, VAMP2, STX1A, STX1B, CPLX1, CPLX2

3. Neurosteroid Systems

Cholesterol Transport & Mitochondrial Import

STAR, TSPO, TSPO2, VDAC1, VDAC2, VDAC3, SLC25A4, SLC25A5, ACBD1, ACBD3, NPC1, NPC2, STARD1, STARD3, STARD4, STARD5, STARD6

Mitochondrial Electron Transfer

FDX1, FDX2, FDXR, POR, CYB5A, CYB5R3

Cholesterol Biosynthesis Terminal

HMGCR, HMGCS1, MVK, PMVK, MVD, IDI1, IDI2, FDPS, FDFT1, SQLE, LSS, CYP51A1, TM7SF2, MSMO1, NSDHL, HSD17B7, SC5D, DHCR7, DHCR24, EBP

Side-Chain Cleavage

CYP11A1

3 β -HSD Isomerase

HSD3B1, HSD3B2, HSD3B7

17 α -Hydroxylase/Lyase

CYP17A1

17 β -Hydroxysteroid Dehydrogenases

HSD17B1, HSD17B2, HSD17B3, HSD17B4, HSD17B6, HSD17B8, HSD17B10, HSD17B11, HSD17B12, HSD17B13, HSD17B14

5 α -Reductases

SRD5A1, SRD5A2, SRD5A3

5 β -Reductase

AKR1D1

3 α -HSD (AKR1C Family)

AKR1C1, AKR1C2, AKR1C3, AKR1C4

20 α -HSD

CBR1

11 β -HSD

HSD11B1, HSD11B2, HSD11B1L

Aromatase

CYP19A1

Adrenal Steroidogenic CYPs

CYP11B1, CYP11B2, CYP21A2

Steroid Sulfotransferases

SULT1E1, SULT2A1, SULT2B1, SULT1A1

Steroid Sulfatase

STS

Steroid UGTs

UGT1A1, UGT1A4, UGT2B7, UGT2B15, UGT2B17, UGT2B4

Steroid-Metabolizing CYPs

CYP7A1, CYP7B1, CYP27A1, CYP46A1, CYP39A1, CYP3A4, CYP3A5, CYP3A7, CYP2D6, CYP1A1, CYP1A2, CYP1B1

Nuclear Steroid Receptors

ESR1, ESR2, AR, PGR, NR3C1, NR3C2

Steroid Receptor Coregulators

NCOA1, NCOA2, NCOA3, NCOR1, NCOR2, NRIP1, PNRC1, PNRC2, PELP1

Membrane Progesterone Receptors

PGRMC1, PGRMC2, PAQR5, PAQR6, PAQR7, PAQR8, PAQR9

Membrane Estrogen Receptor

GPER1

Membrane Androgen-Related

GPRC6A, OXER1, SLC39A9

Steroid Binding Proteins

SHBG, SERPINA6, ALB, AFP, TTR

Steroid Chaperones

FKBP4, FKBP5, PPID, PTGES3

GABA-A Receptor Subunits (Neurosteroid-Sensitive)

GABRA2, GABRA3, GABRA4, GABRA5, GABRA6, GABRB1, GABRB3, GABRD, GABRE, GABRG1, GABRG2, GABRG3, GABRP, GABRQ, GABRR1, GABRR2, GABRR3

Sigma Receptors

SIGMAR1, TMEM97

Xenobiotic Steroid Receptors

NR1I2, NR1I3

Oxysterol Receptors

NR1H3, NR1H2

Neurosteroid Transporters

ABCB1, ABCC1, ABCC4, ABCG2, SLC22A8, SLC22A6, SLCO1A2, SLCO2B1, SLC10A1, SLC10A6

Neurosteroid Transcription Factors

NR5A1, NR5A2, NR0B1, GATA4, GATA6, SP1, SREBF1, SREBF2, NR4A1, NR4A2

Endozepines

DBI

Neurosteroid Signaling Kinases

SRC, PIK3R1

Additional Steroid Reductases

DHRS9, DHRS4, RDH5, WWOX, PECR

4. Glutamatergic Systems

NMDA Receptors

GRIN2C, GRIN2D, GRIN3A, GRIN3B

AMPA Receptors

GRIA1, GRIA2, GRIA3, GRIA4

Kainate Receptors

GRIK1, GRIK2, GRIK3, GRIK4, GRIK5

Delta Receptors

GRID1, GRID2

Glutamate Receptor Interacting Proteins

GRIP1, GRIP2, PICK1, SHANK1, SHANK2, SHANK3, HOMER1, HOMER2, HOMER3, DLGAP1, DLGAP2, DLGAP3, DLGAP4, DLG1, DLG2, DLG3, DLG4

Glutamate Transporters

SLC1A1, SLC1A2, SLC1A3, SLC1A6, SLC1A7, SLC17A6, SLC17A7, SLC17A8

Glutamate Metabolism

GLUL, GLS, GLS2, GLUD1, GLUD2, GAD1, GAD2

BDNF-TrkB Pathway

BDNF, NTRK2, NGF, NTRK1, NTF3, NTRK3, NTF4

mTOR Pathway

MTOR, RPTOR, RICTOR, MLST8, AKT1, AKT2, AKT3, PIK3CA, PIK3CB, PIK3CD, PIK3CG, PTEN, TSC1, TSC2, RHEB, RPS6KB1, RPS6KB2, EIF4EBP1, EIF4E

CREB Pathway

CREB3, CREB5, ATF1, ATF2, ATF3, ATF4, CRTC2, CRTC3

Immediate Early Genes

ARC, FOS, FOSB, FOSL1, FOSL2, JUN, JUNB, JUND, EGR1, EGR2, EGR3, EGR4, NPAS4

CaMKII Signaling

CAMK2A, CAMK2B, CAMK2D, CAMK2G, CAMK4, CALM1, CALM2, CALM3, CALML3, CALML4, CALML5, CALML6

PKA-PKC Signaling

PRKACA, PRKACB, PRKACG, PRKAR1A, PRKAR1B, PRKAR2A, PRKAR2B, PRKCB, PRKCD, PRKCE

Sigma-Metabolic

SIGMAR1, CYP2D6, CYP3A4, CYP2B6, CYP2C19

5. Synaptic Pruning

Complement System

C1QA, C1QB, C1QC, C3, C4A, C4B, ITGAM, ITGB2, C3AR1, MASP1, MASP2, CFH, CFI, CFB, SERPING1

Microglial Signaling & Phagocytosis

CX3CR1, CX3CL1, TREM2, TYROBP, CD68, MERTK, AXL, TYRO3, GAS6, PROS1, MEGF10, GULP1, ABCA1, CD36, CD47, P2RY12, P2RY6, TMEM119

Classical Synaptic Pruning (Adhesion)

NRXN1, NRXN2, NRXN3, NLGN1, NLGN2, NLGN3, NLGN4X, CBLN1, CBLN2, CBLN4

Semaphorin-Plexin Signaling

SEMA3A, SEMA3F, SEMA4D, SEMA6A, SEMA7A, PLXNA1, PLXNA2, PLXNA3, PLXNA4, PLXNB1, PLXNB2, NRP1, NRP2

Ephrin Signaling

EPHA4, EPHA7, EPHB1, EPHB2, EPHB3, EFNA1, EFNA2, EFNA3, EFNA4, EFNA5, EFNB1, EFNB2, EFNB3

WNT Signaling

WNT5A, WNT7A, WNT7B, FZD3, FZD5, RYK, LRP6, DVL1, CTNNB1, APC

TGF- β /BMP Signaling

TGFB1, TGFB2, TGFB1, TGFB2, BMP4, BMP7, BMPR1A, BMPR2, SMAD2, SMAD3, SMAD4

Apoptotic & Caspase Pathways

CASP3, CASP6, CASP9, BAX, BAK1, BCL2, BCL2L1, APAF1, XIAP, FENNA5

Ubiquitin-Proteasome System

FBXO45, MIB1, SMURF1, SMURF2, NEDD4, TRIM3, MYCBP2, USP14

Cytoskeletal Remodeling

RHOA, RAC1, CDC42, ROCK1, ROCK2, LIMK1, CFL1, CFL2, PAK1, ARPC2, WASF1, DAAM1

MHC Class I Molecules

B2M, HLA-A, HLA-B, HLA-C, TAP1, TAP2, PSMB8, PSMB9, CD3Z, LILRB3

Autophagy-Related

ATG5, ATG7, ATG12, BECN1, ULK1, MAP1LC3A, MAP1LC3B, SQSTM1, AMBRA1, RUBCN

Matrix Metalloproteinases

MMP2, MMP9, MMP14, TIMP1, TIMP2, ADAM10, ADAM17, ADAMTS4

Cell Adhesion Molecules

NCAM1, L1CAM, CNTN1, CNTN2, CDH2, PCDH10, PCDHGA1, PCDHGB1, PCDHGC3

Lipid Signaling

APOE, CLU, LDLR, LRP1, ABCA7, PLCG1, DGKZ

Ion Channels & Receptors (Non-Glutamatergic)

GABRA1, GABRB2, GABBR1, KCNJ10, SCN1A, CACNA1C, HCN1

Immune/Inflammatory Modulators

IL1B, IL6, IL10, TNF, IFNG, STAT3, RELA, NFKB1, TLR2, TLR4, NLRP3

Activity-Dependent & Developmental Regulators

SYNGAP1, FMR1, MECP2, LYNX1, OTX2, PVALB, SLC32A1, NPTX2, PENK

Astrocyte-Related

SPARC, SPARCL1, THBS1, THBS2, THBS4, GFAP, AQP4, GJA1

Schizophrenia/Disorder-Associated

CSMD1, MIR137, ZNF804A, DISC1, ERBB4, NRG1, RELN, TCF4

Additional Pruning Regulators

CYFIP1, DSCAM, SDK1, SDK2

6. Circadian Clock

Core Clock Positive Limb

CLOCK, ARNTL, ARNTL2, NPAS2

Core Clock Negative Limb

PER1, PER2, PER3, CRY1, CRY2

Secondary Stabilizing Loop

NR1D1, NR1D2, RORA, RO RB, RORC

Clock-Controlled Feedback

DBP, TEF, HLF, NFIL3, BHLHE40, BHLHE41

Casein Kinases

CSNK1D, CSNK1E, CSNK1A1, CSNK2A1, CSNK2A2, CSNK2B

Other Circadian Kinases

GSK3A, GSK3B, PRKAA1, PRKAA2, CDK5, DYRK1A, PRKCA, PRKCG

Circadian Phosphatases

PPP1CA, PPP1CB, PPP1CC, PPP5C, PPM1G

Circadian Ubiquitin Ligases

FBXL3, FBXL21, FBXW7, BTRC, FBXW11, SIAH2, HUWE1, UBE3A

Circadian Deubiquitinases

USP2, USP7

Circadian Chromatin Modifiers

SIRT1, SIRT6, HDAC1, HDAC2, HDAC3, KDM5A, KMT2A, KMT2C, EZH2, WDR5, SETD2, KAT2A, KAT2B, EP300, CREBBP, EHMT2, PRMT5

Circadian RNA Processing

CIRBP, RBM3, RBM4, HNRNPD, HNRNPK, NONO, SFPQ, THRAP3, FUS, METTL3, YTHDF2, ALKBH5

Circadian Cytoplasmic Regulators

TIMELESS, TIPIN, NUCKS1, KPNB1, XPO1

Circadian Input & Entrainment

OPN4, OPN5, GRIN1, GRIN2A, GRIN2B, ADCYAP1, ADCYAP1R1, SIK1, SIK3, CREB1, CRTCL1, MAPK1, MAPK3

Circadian Output & Coupling

VIP, VIPR2, AVP, AVPR1A, GRP, GRPR, PROK2, PROKR2, NMS

Metabolic Clock Integrators

PPARGC1A, PPARA, PPARG, PPARD, HIF1A, NAMPT, NMNAT1, OGT, SIRT3

Additional Clock-Associated

CIPC, PASD1, CIART, FBXO3, SKP1, CUL1, PDP1, MYBBP1A, GNB2L1, SERPINE1, WEE1, TP53